

Design and Analysis of Helical Spring for a Four Wheeler

¹Alagar Krishna Kumar, ²Dullam Ayyappa

¹Assistant Professor, ²Assistant Professor

¹Mechanical Engineering,

¹Sri Vasavi Engineering College(SVEC), Tadepalligudem, West Godavari, India

Abstract : Suspension system is the word that is a combination of spring systems, shock absorbers and links, these all are connected to the wheels of vehicle. Whenever tire hits a bump, the reaction force will be developed and this reaction force is reduced by using suspension system. The rate how much the reaction force is generated is completely relies on the unsprung weight and these are situated at assembly of each wheel. If the ratio between sprung weight to unsprung weight is larger than the vehicle body and passengers present in the vehicle are affected less by obstructions on the road. In this manuscript helical spring of a car is designed. In suspension crucial part to design is spring. The present paper deals with the helical spring and it is 3D modelled using creo 2.0. Analysis is done using Ansys 14.5. Structural analysis has performed on helical spring by altering material for the spring, Beryllium Copper, Structural Steel, Titanium alloy and Phosphor bronze. This analysis is carried out by the consideration of load acting on the suspension system. Structural analysis has performed on different materials for strength validation and Compared stress values for these materials to know the best suitable material for the spring.

IndexTerms – Suspension, helical spring, unsprung weight.

I. INTRODUCTION

The first shock absorber was called Snubber which was invented by Claude Foster who was the founder of Gabriel company in 1970. The shock absorber of gas type first came in the year 1967 by Gabriel company, from here onwards other markets started duplicating the product. In the initial periods of 20th century, the renowned brand is Houdaille brand and it becomes a generalized brand for the shock absorber, but then it vanished from usage. The device that is modelled to flat shock impulse is known shock absorber and it converts kinetic energy to another form of energy. Suspension system is used for double purpose first thing is keeping road holding capacity of car smoothly because of that smooth driving conditions can be achieved and second thing is providing safety to the vehicle body and occupants in the vehicle from vibrations and bumps etc. Non-dependent front suspension systems was used in most of modern vehicles. On comparison with non-dependent suspension front suspension systems, non-dependent rear suspension systems was used in many vehicles. All the wheels present in the non-dependent rear suspension systems are operated independently. Fully non-dependent suspension system consists of non-dependent suspension on each and every wheel. Swing axle non-dependent suspension system were used in early periods. Now Trailing arms, Wishbone suspensions and Macpherson strut suspension systems are used as a non-dependent suspension systems are used in modern vehicles. Suspension system helps to keep the wheels in firm contact with the roads and also it provides smooth ride.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

In the current project helical spring of a four wheeler is designed. The position of springs in automobile is in between vehicle body and road wheels. Whenever wheel hits the bump, the wheel will be rises and deflection of springs takes place, then spring will stores the energy. While releasing, the spring will rebounds and expends the stored energy due to elasticity of material of the spring. Thus the vibration of spring takes place. Due to internal friction in the materials used for the spring and rubbing at the joints of suspension, amplitude will decreases gradually and vibrations will decreases gradually to zero. To keep the longer time vibrations there is need to choose suitable material for the helical spring.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Achyut P. Banginwar [1] in his project a model of shock absorber be designed and modelled by pro/Engineer. Modal and structural analysis is completed on shock absorber through changing the spring material to Phosphor bronze and structural steel. Structural and modal analysis is finished on the shock absorber to validate the strength and to find out the displacement for diverse frequencies and for different mode numbers. Modal analysis is completed between the two materials to confirm the best suitable material of the two for the design of the spring. By doing this analysis on the spring, for both the materials the author found that structural steel is better material properties than Phosphor bronze.

Mr. Sudarshanamatande [2] the author has designed the shock absorber and modelled it and analyzed it at different loads. In this the analytical values of the stresses are lower than the allowable limit. The stresses are obtained in the finite element analysis for the shock absorber and its components are lower than the allowable limits.

Prince Jerome Christopher J [3] the shock absorber designed and modelled using pro/engineer. This analysis had carried by varying spring coil diameter at different varying loads to validate the spring strength . This analysis is done by considering the mass of the bike and varying the number of persons settled on the bike. The comparison is made by altering the coil diameter of wire to check the best dimensions for helical spring.

Pinjarla. Poornamohan [4] the author has analyzed the shock absorber by shifting the spring material to structural steel and beryllium copper. Modal and structural analysis is completed on shock absorber for structural strength validation and to find out the displacement of the spring for the diverse frequencies and for different mode numbers. Contrast is made between the materials to confirm the best suitable material for the design of the spring.

IV. METHODOLOGIES

The dimensions are acquired from the Maruti Suzuki Dzire. By using the dimensions taken, modeled the object using creo software and after that imported the model into Ansys for further analysis. The following are the dimensions obtained:

Spring specifications:

Diameter of the wire = 15mm

Coil outer diameter = 115 mm

Coil inner diameter = 85 mm

Coil mean diameter = 100 mm

Pitch = 30 mm

Spring length = 200 mm

Analysis steps:

The following steps are required to perform the static structural analysis

a) Import the model into Ansys in IGES format

b) select the suitable material

c) Define Material properties

d) Generate the mesh to obtain accurate values

e) specify loads and constraints

f) solve the model

g) View Results

Theoretical Calculations:

Major diameter of the spring $D_0 = 115$ mm

Minor diameter of the spring $D_i = 85$ mm

Mean spring diameter $D = 115 + 85/2 = 100$ mm

spring coil wire diameter (d) = 15 mm

Free length of the spring = 200 mm

Coil turns number $n = 8$

Consider avg. weight of the car = 1500 kg

Avg. weight of a person = 70 kg

Assuming number of persons as 4

Total weight acts on the vehicle = $1500 + 4(70) = 1780$ kg

Load acting at each side of the vehicle = $1780/4 = 445$ kg

After Converting into Newton's (W) = $445 * 9.81 = 4365.45$ N

Spring index $C = D/d = 100/15 = 6.6$

Spring rate $K = (4C - 1) / (4C - 4) + (0.615/C) = ((26.4 - 1) / (26.4 - 4) + (0.615/6.6)) = 1.1339 + 0.093 = 1.2278$

Formula for Maximum shear stress $T = K * 8 * W * C / \pi d^2$

by substituting the values we get = $(1.2278 * 8 * 4365.45 * 6.6) / (\pi * 15^2) = 400.12$ N/mm²

$$= 4.0012 * 10^8 \text{ N/m}^2$$

$$= 400.12 \text{ MPa}$$

The above value is the maximum shear stress value obtained by substituting all the calculated values. By considering this value as a reference comparing made to be done with the experimental values obtained from the Ansys software.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The four materials are used to find the stresses developed in the helical spring. The materials used in this analysis are structural steel, Beryllium copper, Titanium alloy and Phosphor Bronze. Out of all these materials which material gives the least stress that material will be suitable for the helical spring and it is the best material to be used for manufacturing.

Material properties

The following table represents the material properties of selected materials.

Table 1: Material properties table

Material	Young's modulus (MPa)	Density (kg/m ³)	Poisson's ratio
Structural steel	200000	7850	0.3
Beryllium copper	128000	8250	0.285
Titanium alloy	116000	4620	0.36
Phosphor Bronze	110310	8900	0.359

Simulation of model on different materials

Fig.1,2:Maximum shear stress for structural steel & Beryllium copper at a load of 4365.45 N

The calculated load value 4365.45N is used to apply on the helical spring and the stresses developed can be shown using the different colors in the above fig.1 and fig.2. The red color indicates maximum stress developed and blue color indicates the least value of stress. The base portion of the helical spring are fixed and there least stress is developed. At the top portion of the spring maximum stresses are developed and which can be shown in red color. The stresses developed for the four materials are found by using Maximum shear stress theory and compared with the theoretical value of maximum shear stress for validation.

Fig.3,4:Maximum shear stress for Titanium alloy & Phosphor Bronze at a load of 4365.45 N

Summary table:

The following table shows maximum shear stress values for the corresponding materials

Table 2:Maximum shear stress for different materials

Material	Maximum shear stress (MPa)
Structural steel	399.96
Beryllium copper	457.43
Titanium alloy	442.63
Phosphor Bronze	442.86

VI. CONCLUSION

In this suspension spring, four different materials like structural steel, Beryllium copper, Titanium alloy and Phosphor bronze were used and applied a constant load of 4365.45N based on the theoretical calculations obtained. The boundary conditions used in the solving model is the bottom portion of the part is fixed and the load is applied at the top which is 4365.45N, because of applying load the stresses will be developed in the spring. Here stress values are compared for different materials.

After analyzing and comparing the results, the spring made with structural steel have less stress value out of all materials and it's stress value is 399.96 Mpa. Beryllium copper alloy material having highest stress value compared to remaining three materials and its stress value is 457.43 MPa.

Next highest stress value material is Phosphor bronze and its stress value is 442.86 MPa. On comparing Titanium alloy and Phosphor bronze, Titanium alloy has less stress value and by comparing these three materials Titanium alloy is the best material than Beryllium copper and Phosphor bronze.

The least stress value material is Structural steel and its stress value is 399.96MPa.Finally after comparing the analyzed stress values Structural steel having the less stress value. So Structural steel is the best suitable material for the spring The following shows graphical representation of the maximum shear stresses values for the corresponding material.

Fig.5: Maximum shear stress for Four different materials

The obtained stress value is very much closer to the theoretical maximum shear stress value. Thus the strength is validated for the model. Finally it concludes that the spring made with structural steel having the high strength and stability and because of possessing less stress the material durability is also high.

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